

Physics-Based Data-Driven rSOC Modeling for Power System Operation: An Interpretability-Enhanced Hybrid Neural Network Agent (Supplementary Information)

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Abstract-- This supplementary material provides model parameters for the Case Study in the Letter to facilitate reproducibility.

Index Terms-- Reversible solid oxide cell, neural network, operation region, power system operation.

I. PARAMETERS IN CASE STUDY

Fig. S1 presents the modified IEEE 33-node system structure used in the Case Study. Nodes 6, 18, 24, and 32 are equipped with 3 MW wind turbines (WTs) and 0.5 MWh batteries (BTs, maximum charge/discharge duration of 2 hours). The rSOC system deployed at node 10 comprises 20 stacks, each consisting of 60 cells connected in series. It is accompanied by 1.5 tons of hydrogen storage (HS, maximum charge/discharge time of 8 hours) and 60 MWh of thermal storage (TS, maximum charge/discharge time of 6 hours). The energy balance cycle for BTs and TS is intraday (24 hours), while HS operates on a weekly cycle (168 hours). The capacity factor of WTs and power load are shown in Fig. S2. Additionally, Tables SI and SII provide parameters of the case study and rSOC module.

Fig. S1. The modified IEEE 33-bus system structure.

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Fig. S2. The capacity factor of WTs and the power load.

TABLE SI

PARAMETERS OF CASE STUDY [S1], [S2]

Parameters	Value	Parameters	Value
N_{stack}	20	LHV	33.3 kWh/kg
N_{cell}	60	C^m	10 kWh/K
T_{min}	1023 K	$P_{cell,min}^{ec}$	0.0717 kW
T_{max}	1123 K	$P_{cell,min}^{ec}$	1.6 kW
T_{avr}	1073 K	$P_{cell,min}^{fc}$	0.035 kW
T_{amb}	298 K	$P_{cell,max}^{fc}$	0.4 kW

TABLE SII

PHYSICAL PARAMETERS OF THE RSOC MODULE [S1], [S2]

Parameters	Value
Fuel electrode support layer (Ni-YSZ)	250 μm
Electrolyte layer (YSZ)	8 μm
Oxygen electrode layer (LSCF-CGO)	55 μm
Effective area	414 cm^2
SOEC Fuel Electrode Feed	10/90 %vol $\text{H}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}$
SOFC Fuel Electrode Feed	96/4 %vol $\text{H}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}$
rSOC Oxygen Electrode Feed	Dry Air
SOEC Oxygen/Fuel Electrode Flow Ratio	1
SOFC Oxygen/Fuel Electrode Flow Ratio	13
SOEC Current Density	0-2 A/cm^2
SOFC Current Density	0-1.2 A/cm^2
SOEC Steam Utilization	90 % H_2O
SOFC Hydrogen Utilization	85 % H_2
rSOC Pressure	1 atm

II. REFERENCES

- [S1] F. R. Bianchi *et al.*, "Modelling and optimal management of renewable energy communities using reversible solid oxide cells," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 334, p. 120657, Mar. 2023.
- [S2] C. Huang *et al.*, "Modeling and optimal operation of reversible solid oxide cells considering heat recovery and mode switching dynamics in microgrids," *Appl. Energy*, vol. 357, p. 122477, Mar. 2024.